

DIGITAL REVOLUTION IN WRITING AS AN ASSET ON
ACADEMIC GROUNDS

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Abstract: The article studies the transformative impact of digital technologies on education, including writing, emphasizing generational discrepancies in the perceptions of computers. It also contemplates on the shift from traditional writing methods to multimodal learning and how digital tools enhance engagement and comprehension. The benefits and challenges of the digital revolution are discussed as well.

Keywords: digital technologies, writing, multimodal learning, education, computers, digital learning, educational revolution.

These days, in all walks of life, such as politics, social relations, community, public pedagogy and education, digital technologies play a great role [1]. Especially, in education, the digitalization has made great changes and brought about many benefits. One of the assets in education, writing has discovered its new corners with the implementation of computers, internet and software programs that allow people to communicate effectively with personal, informational, political or commercial aims.

These changes, however, caused different reactions by representatives of different generations to the offers of digital tools. For example, older generations,

who use computers, are more bound to look at computers as a means of typing and printing, whereas younger generations see video gaming and internet-oriented virtual world, when they see computers. Also, younger people today are not satisfied (or less patient) with mono-representation of information in textual form, rather giving their preference to visual and video forms of expression [2]. Obviously, multimodality seems to make the information more attractive to consume and keeps learners' concentration on higher levels for longer period of time. Additionally, this leads to better grasp or memorization of knowledge. Education today can offer a great deal of captivating ways to consume information so as it can be easily digested and applied in practice accordingly. However, this wasn't the case in the past.

Jim Porter remembers his years at school when he first was taught how to write letters, back in 1960, and he recalls how first they were told to write printed letters and then cursive ones. He says a lot of practice was allocated to write beautifully with all the shapes and sizes right back then, and that only later they were required to be more careful with spelling and legibility of prose. The writer thinks such practice of writing brought "to fixate on appearance rather than content", however, he believes readability was important [3].

Later, Internet and digital technology have made massive alterations in the ways traditional lesson would be delivered in all corners of the world [4]. Not only there has been a transition in education with the introduction of a computer and internet as a source of information, but also, mobile learning emerged as a modern educational tool which could easily integrate education with daily life, along with language learning [5].

Nevertheless, not all scholars are ready to face the digital revolution. For example, in "From Pencils to Pixels" Dennis Baron examined the history of writing technology starting from a pencil, to the typewriter, to the modern computer as a writing tool. The scientist wondered and opposed to why we should think that computers are revolutionary literacy technology. He regarded computers

to be just as pencils or typewriters - tools to express our thoughts and that writing itself, and language we use to communicate, had not changed with the revolution of the tools. He says “Why should we get excited about the computer as revolutionary literacy technology? We didn’t get excited about the pencil. We didn’t start a field called “pencils and writing””. According to Jim Porter, the difference between pencils and computers is huge. Pencils were important at certain time, because ability to use it without an eraser back then would require a long period of training and mastery, that is using a pencil without making any mistakes. Pencils were valuable in a way that they would encourage learners to commit themselves to training, discipline, practice and theologically, the pencil was something special that was gifted from god to create and provide its *raison d’etre*. Baron misunderstood the revolution: the revolution was not about the computer itself as a typing tool. Of course, there was nothing exciting about the computer as just a typing tool. It was about computer-based word-processing that made it revolutionary; the network it creates among different computers; the social/rhetorical contexts that are shaped with such virtual networks and publishing practices made the computer of prime breakthrough in science [3].

Undoubtedly, computers and all subsequent digital advancements made education by far more productive and convenient to progress.

Today almost everyone uses a mobile phone and is a user of a social media network or website. In fact, the keenest members of social media have been considered to be millennials [6, 7].

Some research results indicate how tightly connected people are to their digital tools for various reasons such as playing games, communication, education, content creation and data searching. Hence, digitalization of our lives is undeniable and irreplaceable [8].

Incorporating digital technologies into education, for example learning English has made it possible for both teachers and learners to stay actively involved in the learning process both in- and outside of the classroom.

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